

The expected advances in fixed access networks for mobile networks

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Workshop : Beyond 50G-PON - can we still use IMDD?

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OCTAPUS

Optical circuit switched time sensitive network architecture for high-speed passive optical networks and next generation ultra-dynamic and reconfigurable central office environments
HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 Advanced Optical Components

Mobile Network Technology Evolutions Beyond 2030

Key messages : Mobile Network Technology Evolutions Beyond 2030

Beyond “G’s”, for a new approach of mobile network technologies evolutions

We expect future network technologies to make the high level of 5G performance accessible to a larger number of devices rather than to improve the maximum performance levels as a given.

A new G requires new network equipment, to be added to or to replace the legacy ones, and to change the user terminals, leading to massive cost and environmental impact.

on the possibility to reuse legacy equipment through software upgrade or not...

A right balance should be found between introducing innovative connectivity services and capitalizing on legacy technologies whenever possible.

KPI	Possible extreme value	5G reference [12]	Complement, e.g., target scenario
User experienced data rate (at cell edge)	300 Mbit/s 100 Mbit/s	300 Mbit/s 50 Mbit/s	dense urban other outdoor environments Note: 250 Mbit/s required for immersive experiences. The majority of identified future usages would require less than a hundred of Mb/s.
Area capacity	3 Tb/s/km ² 450 Gb/s/km ²	750 Gb/s/km ² 100 Gb/s/km ²	dense urban outdoor & wide area Note: 30% activity factor assumed
Connection density	35 000 / km ² 15 000 / km ² 1.10 ⁶ / km ²	25 000 / km ² 10 000 / km ² 1.10 ⁶ / km ²	mobile broadband – dense urban mobile broadband – urban macro massive IoT
Positioning accuracy	< 10cm < 1m	1m 3m	indoor deployment outdoor & wide area
Energy efficiency	x10 vs. 5G	no quantitative requirement	at least as much as capacity increase, so that the network energy consumption remains stable or decreases
Minimum end-to-end latency	5 ms 0.5 ms (URLLC)	0.5 ms 0.5 ms	in generic deployments, for services that require it for specific services & uses cases associated to specific deployments
Reliability	99.9 % 99.999 %	idem idem	for most of services, typically (mobile broadband) for specific services & uses cases associated to specific deployments
Mobility	500 km/h	idem	for specific services (very high speed trains, planes)

Some features under discussions...

Frequency range FR3 (7.125 to 24.25 GHz) for radio coexistence
but might in conflict with public radio bands

Higher order MIMO and narrower beamforming
→ facilitate multi-user configuration within a cell

Sub-THz bands for deeper radio sensing

Public radio access points in various locations (transport nodes or shopping malls)
Offer local high-speed connectivity
potentially support mm-Wave small cells' backhaul needs

Satellite communication included as Radio Access Network
Specific interconnections to ensure real-time seamless
communication and connect the unconnected

**Data-rate capacity
x 10**

New Applications

**Seamless
communications**

Orange's access networks technologies

Access network segment :

- for Residential based on PON technologies
- for Mobile backhauling & business on PtP

Orange's access networks technologies

Access infrastructure medium

Medium

Only Copper

Full Fiber

New Fiber?

PON technologies

Operational deployment for FTTH

Hardware

G-PON
2,5/1,25 Gbit/s

XGS-PON
10 Gbit/s

HS-PON
50 Gbit/s

VHS-PON
200 Gbit/s

? Orange considers HS-PON as the next step but no deployment request already identified by Orange

PtP technologies (FTT Cell Site)

100 Mbit/s
(G.985)

1 Gbit/s
(G.986)

PtP WDM 1.25
2.5, 10 Gbit/s
(G.989)

10 Gbit/s
25 Gbit/s
50 Gbit/s
100 Gbit/s
(G.9806)

WDM PON
(G.9802)

200 Gbit/s
400 Gbit/s
IEEE802.3dk

Operational deployment for FTT Cell Site (mobile backhaul)

- Standard started
- Standard finished
- Deployment begins
- Deployment ends

2000 2005 2010 2015 2020 2025 2030 2035 2040

PtP optical access to serve 5G and post-5G

OLT shelf

PtP cards
10GEth
(16 ports)

Existing optical access connectivity

- for distributed RAN (in other word no Centralized RAN, no extended reach fronthaul), only Mobile backhaul
- 10GEth PtP is the regular connectivity required for Mobile backhaul (single fiber, bidirectional)
- 25GEth PtP is ready but not purchased
- OLT switching capacity : about 3 to 10Tbit/s

Future optical access connectivity

- 25GEth PtP is ready but could be purchased
- OLT switching capacity evolution : about 100Tbit/s
- 100GEth PtP bidirectional (single fiber) is available (ITU & IEEE specifications in final discussion)
- 200 to 800 Gbit/s (1,6Tbit/s) is under investigation for PtP bidi
- new PtP transceivers include advanced signal processing, new FEC, coherent technology....
- for a tight synchronization, the transceiver parameters must be considered: cf. next slide

Tight Sync – Importance of transceiver latency

Module i is PTP Transmitter port for node A
 Latency of Rx of module i: $R_i = R_{0i} + \Delta R_i$
 Latency of Tx of module i: $T_i = T_{0i} + \Delta T_i$

Module j is PTP Receiver port for node B
 Latency of Rx of module j: $R_j = R_{0j} +/- \Delta R_j$
 Latency of Tx of module j: $T_j = T_{0j} +/- \Delta T_j$

T-BC Node classes

G.8273.2 “node” accuracy classes	Class A	Class B	Class C
Max constant time error	+/-50ns	+/-20ns	+/-10ns

Pluggable classes, derived by node classes (fixed % of the node cTE budget)

	Class A.10	Class A.20	Class B.10	Class B.20	Class C.2	Class C.10
Max constant cTE budget allocated to one pluggable	+/- 5ns	+/-10ns	+/- 2ns	+/- 4ns	+/- 0.2ns	+/- 1ns
ΔT_{max}	+/-5ns	+/-10ns	+/-2ns	+/-5ns	+/-0.2ns	+/-1ns
ΔR_{max}	+/-5ns	+/-10ns	+/-2ns	+/-5ns	+/-0.2ns	+/-1ns

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PON to serve 5G and post-5G?

Why PON is not massively used for Mobile backhauling?

- No alignment of the roadmaps of FTTH and Mobile backhaul:
 - typ. In 2020, 5G cell site required 10GEth, when XGS-PON is launched in 2024
 - An existing fiber infrastructure PtP dedicated to each antenna (with dedicated boxes) to decrease unavailability (historic of SDSL vs. ADSL for 2G and 3G)
 - Each OLT shelf (up to 16k residential customers) has limited number of antenna site within the coverage area :
 - high density area : up to 20 cell sites (never several antenna sites per ODN)
 - medium density area : <5 cell sites
- So PON is a solution that is not massively replicated (not the same scale)
- Need a specific ONU compatible with synchronization (low volume but fully PON interoperable)
 - PON is based on aggregation mechanism, CU&DU is also aggregation based, PON for mobile backhaul is a cascaded of two aggregation mechanisms.
 - Fair play aggregation mechanism not at the same scale for OLT PON port:
 - each home is about 4 final users (64 split ratio \approx 256 final users per OLT port)
 - one cell site is about 2k final users

Why PON could be used for Mobile backhauling?

- Decrease the cost of Mobile backhaul price
- Fiber is now everywhere and could be used for new or remodeling cell sites

Photonics in 6G related to Orange's access networks

Challenges for future mobile networks by

RUs need SFPx form factor with

- Low power consumption - max 2.5 W
- High(er) temperatures - I-temp (and higher)
- Long life span - 15 years

Increased data rates

- LLS (fronthaul) RU and DU gray à 50G, 100G
- BiDi to save fiber need to combat chromatic dispersion and reflections/multi-path interference

O-band vs C-band for WDM

“Coherent lite” - Coherent technologies for mobile: small formfactor/power, bidi BiDi, short reach:

- LLS (fronthaul) Distances: 30km+

Increasingly tight timing synchronization need characterization of impact from optical pluggables

Easier operations with better network management and automation

Other connectivity for future mobile networks

Optical **bypass** inside the OLT for specific use cases (latency)

- photonic **backplane**
- photonic **circuit** (switching)
- continuity of **wavelength** allocation with new **management**

Related fixed access technologies to serve radio access networks

Key points for fixed access networks to serve future mobile networks

- 1 To be ready for a mass market 100Gbit/s PtP bidirectional (single fiber) operation with reach up to 60 km
- 2 Next generation OLT shelf with several 10's Tbit/s switching capabilities and uplink working at 800 Gbit/s or more
- 3 Open question : When do we need to add “all photonics” (IOWN) functions at OLT node?

Thank You

Existing **passive optical** transport solution for outdoor Mobile fronthaul

- **“0 Watt”** solution (passive) is used to save fiber between cell sites and central office node
- **Fiber and wavelength allocation are not line rate dependent**
- **Potential complex colorized transceiver operation**
- **No dedicated transport management (passive demarcation point)**
- **Required dark fiber offers (by wholesale or other)**

Existing **active optical** transport solution for outdoor Mobile fronthaul

- Active solution (about 100 watt) is used to save fiber between cell sites and central office node
- Grey optical transceivers operations (low cost vs. colorized transceivers)
- Ports, card & shelf are line rate and protocol dependents (renewal of transport equipment to be planned cyclically)
- Interoperability between providers
- Potential special features required: time sensitive, slice management,...
- Transport management allowing to provide demarcation points with KPI

